

**TIME SERIES ANALYSIS ON THE PREVELENCE OF MALARIA USING
AUTOREGRESSIVE INTEGRATED MOVING AVERAGE
(A CASE STUDY OF UNIVERSITY OF ILORIN TEACHING HOSPITAL)**

BY

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ATTESTATION

This is to testify that this project titled “**Time series analysis on the number of malaria patient in UITH**” is an original work by **Oguntoye George Adeshina** with matriculation number **20/56EG138** under my supervision.

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this research work carried out by OGUNTOYE, GEORGE ADESHINA with Matriculation number 19/56EG138 was approved as meeting the requirement for the Award of B.Sc. in Statistics from the Department of Statistics, Faculty of Physical Sciences, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria

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DEDICATION

This research work is dedicated to Almighty God who has given me the strength, wisdom, and grace to complete this project to the best of my abilities. It is also dedicated to my entire family member the Oguntoye' s and the Adekanye's for their unconditional love, care, guidance, and support.

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ABSTRACT

Malaria has generated a lot of health challenges nationwide in Nigeria. Despite efforts by individuals, the Nigerian government, and non-government organizations (NGOs) in combating this menace, it still poses a significant threat to society. This research aims to determine the monthly change in the number of malaria patients admitted to the University of Ilorin Teaching Hospital (UITH) from 2013 to 2023 using ARIMA (Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average) time series analysis. The time plot of the monthly number of malaria patients in UITH shows upward and downward movement. The presence of steps also indicates a sudden change in the number of people affected with malaria. The decomposition of data on monthly malaria patients at UITH reveals an underlying trend, seasonal fluctuations, and random variations in the observed data. Test for stationarity using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test was carried out which showed that the original data (series) is stationary at level. The autocorrelation function (ACF) and partial autocorrelation (PACF) plot were used to suggest possible ARMA models.

The ARIMA (3,0,3) was adjudged the best model and was used to forecast for 24 months point values for number of malaria patient (Jan 2024 – Dec 2025). The fitted model of ARIMA(3,0,3) is expressed as $y_t = 47.1130 - 0.1166y_{t-1} - 0.2398y_{t-2} + 0.4982y_{t-3} + 0.7324\varepsilon_{t-1} + 0.7406\varepsilon_{t-2} + 0.2596\varepsilon_{t-3}$. The forecast shows that the average number of malaria patients over the two years is approximately 44 per month.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND STUDY OF MALARIA

Malaria remains a significant global health challenge, primarily affecting populations in tropical and subtropical regions. It is a mosquito-borne infectious disease caused by parasites of the genus *Plasmodium*. The parasite undergoes a complex life cycle, involving both humans and female *Anopheles* mosquitoes as hosts. In humans, the parasite infects red blood cells, leading to a diverse range of symptoms including fever, chills, headache, and fatigue. Severe cases can result in organ failure, coma, and death, primarily affecting young children and pregnant women (WHO, 2023).

Despite significant progress in malaria control, the disease persists as a major public health concern. Factors such as climate change, insecticide and drug resistance, and socioeconomic disparities contribute to the ongoing burden of malaria. Several research works that incorporated integrated vector management, early diagnosis, and effective treatment in combating the disease as also been conducted in the past. At this point there is need to develop a model that can adequately predict the future incidence of the malaria patients. This analysis is crucial for assessing the effectiveness of existing malaria control, intervention and prevention strategies in Nigeria and for guiding future policy and resource

allocation. Therefore, the aim of this study is to fit a time series model to reported cases of malaria patients from 2013 to 2023 in UITH, Ilorin, Kwara state, Nigeria. Additionally, identifying seasonal variations and long-term trends can also help in planning timely interventions to reduce the incidence and impact of malaria in the region.

1.2 HISTORY OF MALARIA

Malaria, a scourge of humanity for millennia, has left an enduring imprint on human history. Ancient civilizations like Egypt, Mesopotamia, and China grappled with its debilitating effects, as evidenced by historical records and mummified remains (Miller et al., 1994). The disease's prevalence contributed to the decline of empires and shaped human migration patterns. By the 20th century, malaria claimed millions of lives annually, particularly in tropical and subtropical regions. While progress has been made in combating malaria, with significant reductions in global incidence, the disease persists as a major public health challenge, disproportionately affecting vulnerable populations in sub-Saharan Africa (WHO, 2022).

According to Philips (1961), Malaria has been a persistent health challenge in Nigeria for centuries, significantly impacting the nation's socioeconomic development. Historical records suggest that the disease was endemic in the region during pre-colonial times, with early European explorers and traders reporting its debilitating effects. The transatlantic slave trade exacerbated malaria's spread, as infected individuals were transported to the

Americas and the Caribbean, contributing to the disease's global distribution. Post-independence, Nigeria grappled with the endemic nature of malaria, which hindered economic growth and public health progress. While significant strides have been made in recent decades, with increased access to insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) and artemisinin-based combination therapies (ACTs), malaria remains a major public health concern (WHO, 2023).

Kwara State, located in northwestern Nigeria, has a long history of malaria endemicity. The state's ecological diversity, characterized by varying climatic conditions and vegetation, has created ideal breeding grounds for malaria-carrying mosquitoes. Historical data on malaria in Kwara State is limited, but it is reasonable to assume that the disease has been a significant health problem for centuries. The socioeconomic implications of malaria in the state have been substantial, with the disease contributing to poverty, reduced productivity, and increased healthcare costs.

Ilorin, the capital of Kwara State, has also experienced the burden of malaria throughout its history. As the state's administrative and commercial center, Ilorin has attracted a diverse population, including people from malaria-endemic regions. This influx of individuals likely contributed to the sustained transmission of malaria in the city. While historical data on malaria in Ilorin is scarce, it is evident that the disease has been a persistent health challenge, affecting both residents and visitors. The city's rapid

urbanization and population growth in recent decades have further compounded the malaria problem (WHO, 2023).

1.3 CURRENT SITUATION OF MALARIA IN NIGERIA, KWARA STATE AND ILORIN

Malaria remains a significant public health challenge in Nigeria, despite concerted efforts to reduce its burden. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), Nigeria carries the heaviest burden of malaria globally, accounting for a substantial proportion of malaria cases and deaths (WHO, 2023). The country's socio-economic development is hindered by the disease, with its impact felt across various sectors, including agriculture, education, and tourism. While progress has been made in recent years through initiatives such as mass distribution of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) and scaling up access to artemisinin-based combination therapies (ACTs), the emergence of drug-resistant malaria parasites and challenges in healthcare delivery continue to pose significant obstacles (National Malaria Elimination Programme, 2023).

Kwara State, like many other Nigerian states, is endemic for malaria. The state's epidemiological profile highlights the persistent threat posed by the disease. Factors such as climate change, population growth, and poverty contribute to the malaria burden in the state. While Kwara State has implemented various malaria control strategies, including indoor residual spraying (IRS) and community-based interventions, the disease continues

to affect a considerable portion of the population, particularly children under five and pregnant women (Kwara State Malaria Control Programme, 2023).

Ilorin, the capital city of Kwara State, reflects the malaria situation in the state as a whole. The city's rapid urbanization and population growth have created challenges in malaria prevention and control. Mosquito breeding sites are prevalent in many parts of the city, facilitating malaria transmission. Despite efforts to improve access to malaria prevention and treatment services, the disease remains a public health concern in Ilorin. The need for sustained malaria control activities, including vector control, case management, and community engagement, is crucial to reduce the malaria burden in the city (Ilorin West Local Government Area Malaria Control Programme, 2023).

Addressing the current malaria situation in Nigeria, Kwara State, and Ilorin requires a multi-faceted approach. Strengthening healthcare systems, increasing access to quality malaria diagnosis and treatment, promoting preventive measures, and conducting research on malaria epidemiology and drug resistance are essential components of malaria control and elimination efforts. Collaboration between government, healthcare providers, communities, and development partners are vital to achieve lasting impact.

1.4 STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Malaria has generated a lot of health challenges nationwide in Nigeria. Despite efforts by individuals, the Nigerian government, and non-government organizations (NGOs) in

combating this menace, it still poses a significant threat to society. This research aims to determine the monthly change in the number of malaria patients admitted to the University of Ilorin Teaching Hospital (UITH) from 2013 to 2023 using ARIMA (Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average) time series analysis. The study will analyze trends and patterns to understand whether there has been a reduction or increase in the number of malaria patients over the years. This analysis is crucial for assessing the effectiveness of existing malaria control and prevention strategies in Nigeria and for guiding future policy and resource allocation. Identifying seasonal variations and long-term trends can also help in planning timely interventions to reduce the incidence and impact of malaria in the region.

1.5 AIM AND OBJECTIVES

The aim of this project is to develop a forecasting model for cases of malaria patient in University of Ilorin Teaching Hospital from January 2013 to December 2023. The specific objectives are to:

- i.** study the pattern of Malaria Patient in UITH using time plot;
- ii.** fit an appropriate model to the number of malaria patient;
- iii.** identify among the models the one that best fit the data under study; and
- iv.** forecast for the incidence of malaria for year 2024.

1.6 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study's findings are important for several reasons. They help with planning and making health policies by showing trends in malaria cases at the University of Ilorin Teaching Hospital (UIITH) from 2013 to 2023, helping officials decide where to use resources and what strategies to implement. The findings also evaluate the effectiveness of malaria control efforts, identify seasonal and long-term trends, and use ARIMA analysis to predict future cases, helping with planning for outbreaks. Additionally, these findings highlight the value of local health data and encourage its use across Nigeria. It is also useful for researchers, students, the Ministry of Health, and other stakeholders by providing important information about malaria trends in Kwara State, improving public health outcomes.

1.7 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This research work deals with the monthly number of malaria patients admitted to the University of Ilorin Teaching Hospital (UIITH) from January 2013 to December 2023. The data was extracted from hospital records to understand past malaria trends and predict future incidence rates. The R programming language was used for time series analysis, specifically employing the ARIMA model to examine the data. The study focuses on identifying trends, seasonal patterns, and forecasting future malaria cases based on historical data. It aims to evaluate the effectiveness of malaria control efforts and provide insights for public health planning specifically for Kwara State, Nigeria.

1.8 LIMITATION OF STUDY

The study is limited to data from the University of Ilorin Teaching Hospital (UIITH) and may not fully represent malaria trends in other regions or hospitals across Nigeria. The accuracy of the findings depends on the completeness and reliability of the hospital's records; any missing or inconsistent data could affect the results. Although the study covers the period from January 2013 to December 2023, it does not account for changes in malaria control measures or healthcare practices outside this timeframe. The ARIMA model, while useful for time series forecasting, may not capture all factors influencing malaria incidence, such as environmental or socio-economic changes. Additionally, the use of R language and its tools may have limitations in handling very large datasets or complex analyses.

1.9 ORGANISATION OF STUDY

The organization of the project work is as follows: Chapter One covers the introductory aspects. Following this, Chapter Two covers the literature review and the methodology used for the study. Chapter Three presents the data, analyzes the findings, and discusses the results. Finally, Chapter Four provides a summary of the study, along with the findings and recommendations.

1.10 DEFINITION OF SOME TERMS

- i. Plasmodium: The genus of parasites responsible for malaria. The most common species affecting humans are *Plasmodium falciparum*, *Plasmodium vivax*, *Plasmodium ovale*, and *Plasmodium malariae*.

- ii.** Anopheles Mosquito: The genus of mosquitoes that transmit malaria parasites. Female Anopheles mosquitoes are responsible for spreading malaria through their bites.
- iii.** Parasitemia: The presence of parasites in the blood. In malaria, it refers to the level or density of malaria parasites in the bloodstream.
- iv.** Vector: An organism that transmits a pathogen from one host to another. In the case of malaria, the vector is the Anopheles mosquito.
- v.** Malaria Endemic: A term describing regions where malaria is consistently present and causes a significant number of cases throughout the year.
- vi.** Chloroquine: An antimalarial drug used to treat and prevent malaria. It works by interfering with the growth of malaria parasites in red blood cells.
- vii.** Artemisinin-based Combination Therapy (ACT): A treatment regimen for malaria that combines artemisinin with another antimalarial drug. It is the recommended treatment for uncomplicated *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria.
- viii.** Erythrocytic Stage: The stage of the malaria parasite's life cycle that occurs inside red blood cells, leading to symptoms like fever and chills.
- ix.** Sporozoite: The stage of the malaria parasite that is injected into the bloodstream by an infected mosquito. It travels to the liver to mature.

- x. Hypnozoites: Dormant liver stages of *Plasmodium vivax* and *Plasmodium ovale* that can reactivate and cause relapse of malaria after the initial infection is treated.
- xi. Malaria Relapse: The recurrence of malaria symptoms due to reactivation of hypnozoites in the liver after initial treatment has been completed.
- xii. Intermittent Preventive Treatment (IPT): A strategy used to prevent malaria in high-risk groups, such as pregnant women or young children, by administering antimalarial drugs at regular intervals.
- xiii. Long-Lasting Insecticidal Nets (LLINs): Mosquito nets treated with insecticides to protect against mosquito bites and reduce malaria transmission.
- xiv. Indoor Residual Spray (IRS): The application of insecticides on indoor surfaces to kill mosquitoes and reduce malaria transmission.
- xv. Rapid Diagnostic Test (RDT): A diagnostic tool used to quickly detect malaria infection by identifying malaria antigens or antibodies in a blood sample.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERAURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

2.1 LITERATURE REVIEW

The geographical areas affected by malaria have shrunk considerably over the past 50 years but control is becoming more difficult and gains are being eroded. So many researchers have carried out research on malaria patient using time series:

Reindolf *et al.* (2018) sought to assess the trends of Malaria incidence in Kumasi Metropolis and forecast future incidence. A retrospective comparative study design was employed using data from the Regional Health Directorate from January 2010 to December 2016. Trend of malaria prevalence was analyzed and compared by years and months. Data used for the study was entirely secondary which was gathered from recorded monthly malaria cases at various hospitals in Kumasi. The Quadratic model was used for the forecasting of the half year incidence of Malaria while Auto regressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) (1, 1, 2) was used for forecasting monthly malaria incidence for the years 2018 and 2019 in Kumasi Metropolis. For the general pattern, July recorded the highest number of cases whereas January recorded the lowest cases in each year. Also, 2010 was the best performing year since it recorded the lowest number of malaria cases (10,336). The projected malaria cases for the first half year of 2018 are expected to be 61,371.8, while the second half year is expected to be 77,842.0. This model is recommended to the metropolitan health directorate and researchers who want to monitor

the malaria reported cases in the metropolis and other parts of the world. It is suggested that measures should be put in place to curb malaria incidence during the period of the year when high incidence were recorded.

Sadiq, (2015) aimed at investigating the change in the trend of malaria cases, effect of meteorological variables on malaria incidence. In addition, he examined the effect of meteorological variables on malaria incidence and forecasted malaria cases for 2014 and 2015 in Ogun State. A trend analysis was performed on the malaria cases to know if there is a monthly or yearly increase or decrease in malaria incidence and would Nigeria meet the millennium development goal for reduction of malaria by 2015. A 10-year time-series analysis from 2004 to 2013 was conducted to evaluate the relationship between climatic variables (rainfall, humidity, minimum and maximum temperature) and malaria cases in Ogun State, Nigeria using an autoregressive moving average (ARIMA) and autoregressive moving average with exogenous variables (ARIMAX). Cross-correlation analysis was then performed to know the association between meteorological variable at lag 0 to 4 and the number of malaria cases. The ARIMAX model was then used to measure the relationship between them. Finally, the projected malaria cases were then forecasted for two years using both the ARIMA and ARIMAX model. The results from his study indicated a monthly increase in malaria cases by 0.7 percent and a yearly increase of 9.0 percent and a monthly rate of 1.749 cases per 100,000 people to a yearly rate of 20.98 cases per 100,000 people. For maximum xix temperature, the model suggests that in Ogun State, Nigeria, for every one-degree centigrade rise in maximum temperature, the number of malaria cases will

decrease between 90.8 and 97.8 percent with a one-month delay. For minimum temperature, one degree rise in minimum temperature may be related to a decrease in the number of malaria cases between 93.4 and 99.4 percent with a three-month delay and one degree rise in minimum temperature may be related to an increase in the number of malaria cases between 0.25 and 6.47 percent with a one-month delay. The total number of predicted numbers of malaria cases was 331,683 and 309,228 for both the ARIMA and ARIMAX model compare to the 2005 malaria cases of 125,229. This shows an increase in malaria cases from 146 percent for the ARIMAX model and 164 percent for the ARIMA model. Sadiq, (2015), concluded that temperature plays a significant role in malaria transmission in Ogun State. Also, Ogun State will not likely meet the millennium development goal for malaria by 2015.

Osador *et al.* (2017), carried out research on Modeling malaria control intervention effect in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa using intervention time series analysis. The time series shows markedly increase in malaria cases. The re-introduction of DDT into the SA malaria control program in March 2000, coincided with the beginning of the abrupt decline of malaria cases in KZN which continued until June 2001. Afterward, relatively low and sustained cases were recorded with a noticeable spike between December 2003 to November 2004. The quick decline in malaria cases after November 2004 and sustained low malaria cases onwards can be attributed to the continuous application of the intervention. Overall, this is a good example of a time series that the impact of the known

intervention is abrupt in onset and permanent in duration. Thus, an empirical assessment of the impact of the known intervention which combines a noise and intervention models is conducted.

Elvis *et al.* (2017) carried out research on Time Series Analysis of Malaria Cases in Kasena Nankana Municipality. The research was undertaken with the prior motive to develop an adequate model for forecasting future trends. It evolved that ARIMA (1, 0, 1) fits the data well. The trend analysis indicated that malaria cases at the Navrongo Municipality was growing at a constant quadratic rate. Therefore, Ministry of Health together with the health workers was advised to intervene in the creation of awareness of this silent killer disease. The model also proved that the model was adequate for forecasting of monthly cases of malaria in the Municipality. Moreover, the model was found to have a good fit hence appropriate for the study. Therefore, hospitals in the Municipality were hinted to expect a reduction in the number of malaria cases.

Dhally *et al.* (2021) conducted a study using data from the northwestern province of Zambia. the study used historical data that considers seasonality patterns at the provincial level to forecast malaria cases on a monthly basis. From January 2014 to December 2020, there were 3,795,541 malaria cases for all ages in northwestern province. In the time series plot of monthly confirmed cases of malaria, there were seasonal trends that were observed. The predicted cases show an expected increase. The forecasted malaria cases provided helped planners and implementers of malaria programs to effectively mobilise resources

and implement effective prevention and elimination measures. Dhally *et al.* (2021) advised that further studies should attempt to evaluate the usefulness of incorporating the forecasting model such as this one into the existing malaria prevention and elimination programs to assess its impact in reducing malaria and the cost of intervention measures.

Ferrao *et al.* (2021) analyzed the malaria temporal variation and model its pattern in Sussundenga District, Mozambique. Data from weekly epidemiological bulletins (BES) was collected from 2015 to 2019 and a time-series analysis was applied. For temporal modeling, a Box-Jenkins method was used with an autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA). Over the study period, 372,498 cases of *P. falciparum* were recorded in Sussundenga. There were weekly and yearly variations in incidence overall ($p < 0.001$). Children under five years had decreased malaria tendency, while patients over five years had an increased tendency.

2.2 METHODOLOGY

2.2.1 Time Series Analysis

A time series is a set of observations taken at equal intervals. It is a sequence of observations ordered in time (or space). If observations are made on some phenomenon over time, it is most sensible to display the data in the order they occurred, particularly since successive observations will probably be dependent.

2.2.2 Time Series as a Stochastic Process

The theory of stochastic processes plays an important role in the investigation of random phenomena depending on time. A time series is a type of stochastic process indexed by time. It is an arrangement of statistical data in chronological order, reflecting the dynamic pace of a phenomenon over a period. Time series are significant in business and economics. Mathematically, a time series is defined by the functional relationship:

$$X_t = f(t)$$

where X_t is the value of the phenomenon (or variable) under consideration at time t .

2.2.3 Time plot

A graphical display of the values or observations recorded chronologically in which the observations are plotted on the vertical axis and the time scale is plotted on the horizontal axis with the plotted points connected adjacently.

2.2.4 Components of Time Series

Time series analysis involves identifying or determining the various influences that interact to produce variations in the time series, and then isolating, studying, analyzing, and measuring them independently by holding others constant. A general time series can be considered as a mixture of four main components: trend, cyclic, seasonal, and irregular variations.

2.2.5 Trend Movements

The general tendency of time series data to increase, decrease, or stagnate over a long period is called a secular trend or simply trend. This is a general direction in which the time plot appears to be moving. A series contains a trend if there is a systematic change in its mean over time; that is, if a relationship exists between the mean and time. This is denoted by:

$$T_t = f(t)$$

2.2.6 Seasonal Variations

Seasonal variations in a time series are due to rhythmic forces that operate in a regular and periodic manner over a span of less than a year, i.e., within 12 months.

2.2.7 Additive Model: In the additive model, the time series can be expressed as:

$$X_t = T_t + S_t + C_t + I_t$$

where X_t is the time series value at time t and T_t , S_t , C_t , and I_t represent the trend, seasonal, cyclical, and irregular variations at time t respectively. The additive model assumes that all four components of the time series operate independently of each other. Therefore, the additive model is adopted in this project work.

2.2.8 Multiplicative Model: The time series can also be represented or expressed as:

$$X_t = T_t \times S_t \times C_t \times I_t$$

This model assumes that the four components of the time series are due to different causes but are not necessarily independent and can affect each other. Considering these points, most economic and business time series are characterized by the classical model

2.2.9 Estimation of Trend

i. Graphic or Free Hand Curve Fitting Method

This is the simplest and most flexible method of estimating the secular trend, which involves fitting a trend line or curve simply by looking at the graph. Its major disadvantage is that it depends too much on individual judgment, although it is very simple and time-saving.

ii. The Least Squares Method

The principle of the least squares method provides an analytical or mathematical device for obtaining an objective fit to the trend of a given time series. Most of the data relating to time series conform to definite laws of growth or decay, making analytical trend fitting more reliable for forecasting and predictions. This technique is used to fit both linear and non-linear trends.

iii. Semi-Average Method

In the semi-average method, the data is divided into two parts. The average of the first part is obtained and plotted against the year that is at the center of that part. The two points are joined to form a straight line. If the data (the years) is odd, the middle year is ignored.

iv. Moving Average Method

The technique of using a moving average involves replacing a particular measurement with the arithmetic mean of a series of measurements of which it is the center. When an odd number is chosen, the moving average is centered as an observed measurement. However, when an even number (order) of measurements is chosen, the moving average is centered between two observed measurements and must be re-centered before comparisons can be made between the average and the measurements. One disadvantage of this method is that the data (values) at the beginning and end of a series are virtually lost.

Suppose we are given the mmm-order Moving Average:

$$M_t = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=\frac{t-(m-1)}{2}}^{\frac{t+(m-1)}{2}} X_i$$

Where M_t is the moving average at time t , mmm is the order of the moving average, and X_i are the observations.

2.2.10 Autocorrelation

An important guide to the properties of a time series is provided by a series of quantities called sample autocorrelation coefficients, which measure the correlation between observations at different lags. The autocorrelation coefficient at lag k is defined as:

$$r_k = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^{n-k} (X_t - \bar{X})(X_{t+k} - \bar{X})}{\sum_{t=1}^n (X_t - \bar{X})^2}$$

Where:

r_k is the autocorrelation coefficient at lag k

n is the number of observations.

X_t is the observation at time t

\bar{X} is the mean of the time series,

An assumption for estimating the parameters through the least squares method is that the error terms are independently and identically normally distributed with a mean of zero and constant variance. If autocorrelation exists, then this assumption fails.

2.2.11 Autocorrelation Function (ACF)

The Autocorrelation Function (ACF) measures the correlation between a time series and its past values at different lags. It helps identify the order of Moving Average (MA) models and detect patterns like seasonality. The ACF values range from -1 to 1, with significant spikes indicating strong correlations at specific lags. The ACF plot, or correlogram, visualizes these correlations and is crucial for understanding the linear relationships within the data and identifying the presence of seasonality or repetitive patterns.

2.2.12 Partial Autocorrelation Function (PACF)

The Partial Autocorrelation Function (PACF) measures the correlation between a time series and its past values, removing the effects of shorter lags. This isolation makes the PACF particularly useful for determining the order of Autoregressive (AR) models. Significant spikes in the PACF plot, or correlogram, indicate strong partial correlations at

specific lags, helping to identify the appropriate AR model order. By focusing on the pure correlation at each lag, the PACF is essential for accurate model specification and forecasting in time series analysis.

2.2.13 The Correlogram

A correlogram is a graphical tool used in time series analysis to display the autocorrelation coefficients (ACF) or partial autocorrelation coefficients (PACF) of a time series for different lags. It helps in identifying the presence and extent of autocorrelation in the data.

2.2.14 ACF Correlogram:

- The ACF correlogram plots the autocorrelation coefficients of the time series against different lag values.
- Each bar in the plot represents the autocorrelation coefficient for a particular lag.
- Significant spikes outside the confidence bounds indicate significant autocorrelations at those lags.

2.2.15 PACF Correlogram:

- The PACF correlogram plots the partial autocorrelation coefficients against different lag values.
- Each bar represents the partial autocorrelation coefficient for a particular lag, controlling for the influence of all shorter lags.

- Significant spikes outside the confidence bounds in the PACF correlogram help identify the order of an autoregressive (AR) process.

2.2.16 Unit Root Test

A unit root test is a statistical test used to determine whether a time series has a unit root, implying that the series is non-stationary and contains a stochastic trend. The null hypothesis of a unit root test is that the time series has a unit root, which means it is non-stationary. Common unit root tests include:

- Dickey-Fuller Test
- Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Test
- Phillips-Perron (PP) Test
- Kwiatkowski-Phillips-Schmidt-Shin (KPSS) Test

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test was used for the research work.

2.2.17 Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Test

The ADF test is a specific type of unit root test developed by Dickey and Fuller. It is an extension of the Dickey-Fuller test that accounts for higher-order autocorrelation in the residuals. The ADF test is formulated as follows:

Null Hypothesis (H_0):

The time series Y_t has a unit root, i.e., it is non-stationary.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁):

The time series does not have a unit root, i.e., it is stationary.

The basic objective of the test is to test the null hypothesis that $\rho=1$ in:

$$Y_t = \rho Y_{t-1} + \epsilon_t$$

Against the one-sided alternative $\rho < 1$. So, in general, we have:

- H₀: the series is non-stationary.
- H₁: the series is stationary.

We usually use the regression:

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha + \beta t + \gamma Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \delta_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + \epsilon_t$$

So that a test of $\rho = 1$ is equivalent to a test of $\gamma = 0$ (since $\rho = \gamma + 1$).

Conclusion:

- Reject H₀: This means there is sufficient evidence at a given level of confidence that the series is stationary.
- Fail to reject H₀: This means that there is no sufficient evidence at a given level of significance that the series is stationary.

2.2.18 Autoregressive (AR) Model

An autoregressive model is when a value from a time series is regressed on previous values from that same time series. For example, y_t on y_{t-1} .

In this regression model, the response variable in the previous time period has become the predictor and the errors have our usual assumptions about errors in a simple linear regression model. The order of an autoregression is the number of immediately preceding values in the series that are used to predict the value at the present time. So, the preceding model is a first-order autoregression, written as AR (1).

If we want to predict y this year y_t using measurements of global temperature in the previous two years (y_{t-1}, y_{t-2}) , then the autoregressive model for doing so would be:

$$y_t = \phi_0 + \phi_1 y_{t-1} + \phi_2 y_{t-2} + \epsilon_t$$

This model is a second-order autoregression, written as AR (2), since the value at time t is predicted from the values at times $t-1$ and $t-2$. More generally, a k th-order autoregression, written as AR(k), is a multiple linear regression in which the value of the series at any time t is a (linear) function of the values at times $t-1, t-2, \dots, t-k$.

2.2.19 Moving Average (MA) Model

We learned that an autoregressive term in a time series model for the variable x_t is a lagged value of x_t . For instance, a lag 1 autoregressive term is x_{t-1} (multiplied by a coefficient). This defines moving average terms.

A moving average term in a time series model is a past error (multiplied by a coefficient). Let $w_t \sim i.i.d N(0, \sigma_w^2)$, meaning that the w_t are identically, independently distributed, each with a normal distribution having mean 0 and the same variance. The first-order moving average model, denoted by MA (1), is:

$$x_t = \mu + w_t + \theta_1 w_{t-1}$$

The second-order moving average model, denoted by MA (2), is:

$$x_t = \mu + w_t + \theta_1 w_{t-1} + \theta_2 w_{t-2}$$

2.2.20 Theoretical Properties of a Time Series with an MA (1) Model:

- Mean is $E(x_t) = \mu$
- Variance is $Var(x_t) = \sigma^2(1 + \theta_1^2)$
- Autocorrelation function (ACF) is $\rho_1 = \frac{\theta_1}{1 + \theta_1^2}$ and $\rho_h = 0$ for $h \geq 2$

Note that the only nonzero value in the theoretical ACF is for lag 1. All other autocorrelations are 0. Thus, a sample ACF with a significant autocorrelation only at lag 1 is an indicator of a possible MA (1) model.

2.2.21 Autoregressive Moving Average (ARMA) Model

For some observed time series, a very high-order AR or MA model is needed to model the underlying process well. In this case, a combined autoregressive moving average (ARMA) model can sometimes be a more parsimonious choice. An ARMA model expresses the conditional mean y_t as a function of both past observations, y_{t-1}, \dots, y_{t-p} and past innovations, $\epsilon_{t-1}, \dots, \epsilon_{t-q}$. The number of past observations that y_t depends on, p , is the **AR** degree. The number of past innovations that y_t depends on q , is the **MA** degree. In general, these models are denoted by ARMA(p,q).

The form of the ARMA(p,q) model is:

$$y_t = c + \phi_1 y_{t-1} + \dots + \phi_p y_{t-p} + \epsilon_t + \theta_1 \epsilon_{t-1} + \dots + \theta_q \epsilon_{t-q}$$

Where ϵ_t is an uncorrelated innovation process with mean zero.

2.2.22 Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA)

This is also known as the Box-Jenkins model. This methodology will be used to forecast the exchange rate of Nigeria Naira to Dollar; the model is based on the assumption that the time series involved are stationary. Stationarity will first be checked and if not found, the series will be differenced d times to make it stationary, and then the Autoregressive Moving Average (ARMA) (p, q) will be applied. The ARIMA procedure provides a comprehensive set of tools for univariate time series model identification, parameter estimation, and forecasting, and it offers great

flexibility in the kinds of ARIMA models that can be analyzed. The ARIMA procedure supports seasonal, subset, and factored ARIMA models; intervention or interrupted time series models; multiple regression analysis with ARMA errors; and rational transfer function models of any complexity.

2.2.23 Box-Jenkins Methodology

In regression models, if the y_t 's are not independent (dependent on different things e.g., time, past values of y , etc.), we should use in our model (for forecasting) past values of the time series variable and/or current and past values of the error terms. This is the basis of the time series methodology called the Box-Jenkins method. This method involves extracting the predictable movement of the variable in question (inflation rate) from previously observed data through a series of iterations. More explicitly, Box-Jenkins employs iteration to tell what the future of a variable will be by using the past data of the variable in question (inflation rate). It is a model that is appropriate for forecasting financial data. It is advisable to use the Box-Jenkins methodology when there is autocorrelation. Furthermore, the procedure is carried out on stationary data. If the data is found not to be stationary, i.e., it contains a trend, it should be made stationary by differencing the data. When using the Box-Jenkins methodology, the data should be dependent, stationary, and autocorrelated.

2.2.24 Advantages of Box-Jenkins Methodology:

- In many cases, it is the most accurate forecasting model for any set of data.
- It offers a more systematic approach to building, analyzing, and forecasting time series models.

Disadvantages of Box-Jenkins Methodology:

- A minimum of 50-100 data points is needed to build a good model.
- Updating the model as new data are acquired is not possible. When there are new data, the model has to be rebuilt from scratch.
- Calculation of the parameters can only be done with the aid of a computer, given its iterative nature.
- The task of finding the correct model is usually time-consuming.

Summary of the Box-Jenkins Methodology

The Box-Jenkins methodology has four steps that will be followed when forecasting the exchange rate as stipulated below:

1. **Model Identification:** This involves finding out the values of p , d , and q , where:
 - p is the number of autoregressive terms.
 - d is the number of times the series is differenced.
 - q is the number of moving average terms.

The identification here will be done based on the correlogram plot obtained. Where both autocorrelation and partial correlation cut off at a certain point, we conclude that the data follows an autoregressive model. The order \mathbf{p} of the ARIMA model is obtained by identifying the number of lags moving in the same direction. In case the series was non-stationary, the number of times we difference the series to obtain stationarity is the value of \mathbf{d} .

2. **Estimation:** This involves the estimation of the parameters of the autoregressive and moving average terms in the model. The nonlinear estimation will be used.
3. **Diagnostic Checking:** Having chosen a particular ARIMA model and having estimated its parameters, we now examine whether the chosen model fits the data reasonably well. The simple test of the chosen model will be done to see if the residuals estimated from this model, are white noise. If they are, we can accept the particular fit, and if not, the model will have to be started over.

2.2.24 Stationary and Non-Stationary Processes

A time series is a record of observations that are time variants (time-dependent). These observations are generally generated by stochastic models that do not have time-variant structures. Such a time series is said to be stationary. A stationary time series is one that has a constant mean and variance. On the other hand, if the stochastic structure of the series itself changes over time, the series is said to be

non-stationary. More explicitly, a non-stationary time series is said to have a time-variant mean and variance.

2.2.25 Test for Stationary Series

A time plot depicts the trend that exists in non-stationary series. For theoretical and practical reasons, the Dickey-Fuller unit root test is mostly used to check for non-stationarity or stationarity in series. However, the ACF and PACF can also be employed. For speed, it is better to use the ACF and PACF to check stationarity when using the Box-Jenkins methodology.

Stationary Time Series: Mean, variance and other statistics of a stationary time series remains constant. Hence, the conclusions from the analysis of stationary series is reliable.

Non-Stationary Time Series Mean, variance and other statistics of a non-stationary time series changes with time. Hence, the conclusions from the analysis of a non-stationary series might be misleading.

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller test is mostly used to check non-stationarity or stationarity in series. If the test reveal that p-value is less than the level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the data is stationary

2.2.26 Differencing

Differencing involves calculating the difference between successive data points in a time series. This technique helps eliminate trends or patterns that develop over time. By using differencing, a non-stationary time series can be transformed into a stationary one. The process involves subtracting the current value in the series from the previous one or from a lagged value. For instance, if Y_t represents the value of a series at time t , the first difference would be $Y_t - Y_{t-1}$. The second difference would be $(Y_t - Y_{t-1}) - (Y_{t-1} - Y_{t-2})$. Differencing can help make a data series stationary by removing trends and seasonal patterns.

Differencing involves computing the differences between consecutive data points in a time series. This process helps remove trends or patterns that evolve over time. A non-stationary time series can be made stationary using the technique of differencing. It entails deducting the current value in the series from either the prior one in the series or from a lagged value. For example, if Y_t is the value of a series at time t , then the first difference of this would be given as $Y_t - Y_{t-1}$. Furthermore, the second difference would be given as $(Y_t - Y_{t-1}) - (Y_{t-1} - Y_{t-2})$. Differencing can make a data series appear stationary by removing trends and seasonal patterns.

2.2.27 Removal of Trend and Ensuring Stationarity

When it comes to medical data, attention has to be paid to their nature of stationarity, as medical data has to be stationary before they are analyzed. If a test,

as described above, is carried out and our data is found to be stationary, further analysis can be done as the data is in the required state. However, if the test reveals that the data is non-stationary, it has to be transformed. When it comes to Box-Jenkins, differencing is the appropriate way of transforming non-stationary data to being stationary. A series is said to be stationary if it contains no trend and seasonal variation. Thus, if a series has a trend, seasonality, and the variance changes with time, the common approach is to difference the series. A seasonal effect can be eliminated by differencing the series with a seasonal period. An appropriately differenced series that contains no trend can be said to be stationary.

2.2.28 Information Criteria

In model identification, autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation functions are used. There may be several adequate models that can be used instead to represent a given set of data. Residuals from all adequate models, the selection criterion is normally based on summary statistics from residuals computed from a fitted model or on forecast errors.

2.2.29 Akaike Information Criterion (AIC)

Akaike proposed a criterion in 1974 for model fitting. This is the Final Prediction Error (FPE), the one-step-ahead prediction error after fitting an AR(p) model:

$$FPE = \frac{SSE}{n - p} \left(1 + \frac{p}{n}\right)$$

Where SSE is the least squares estimate of the residual variance after an AR(p) model, and n is the number of observations. An improvement of this was given by Akaike (1977):

$$AIC(M) = -2 \ln(\text{maximum likelihood}) + 2M$$

The AIC criterion then reduces to:

$$AIC = n \ln \left(\frac{SSE}{n} \right) + 2M$$

Where M is the number of parameters. The optimal order of the model is then given by the value MMM, which is a function of p and q, for which AIC(M) is minimized.

2.2.30 Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC)

In 1976, Schiavetto showed that the AIC criterion tends to overestimate the order of the autoregression. Akaike (1976, 1979) has recently developed an extension due to this. This is given by:

$$BIC = \ln(n) M + \ln(n) \ln (SSE)$$

Where M is the number of parameters and n is the sample variance of the series.

2.2.31 Corrected Akaike Information Criterion (AIC_c)

This is AIC with a correction for finite sample sizes. The formula for AICC depends upon the statistical model. Assuming that the model is univariate, linear, and has normally-distributed residuals (conditional upon regressors), the formula for AICC is as follows:

$$AICc = AIC + \frac{2M(M + 1)}{n - M - 1}$$

Where n denotes the sample size and k denotes the number of parameters.

2.2.32 Diagnostic Checking

This is the next stage after parameter estimation. The adequacy of the model needs to be checked. The model assumptions need to be satisfied. The conditions can be summarized as follows:

1. The iterative process of parameter estimation must converge; i.e., the process stops when no other parameter estimates (with a relative change of less than 0.001) can be found that yield a smaller SSE.
2. The invertibility and/or stationarity conditions should be satisfied.
3. The residuals (forecast errors) should be random and approximately normally distributed.
4. All parameter estimates should be significantly different from zero, i.e., significant t-ratios.
5. The model should be parsimonious, i.e., in its simplest form.
6. The model should have a small RMSE. The basic assumption is that ϵ_t are white noise, i.e., there are uncorrelated random shocks with zero mean and constant variance. The residual series ϵ_t are analyzed to check whether the residuals are white noise. The sample ACF and PACF of the residuals are computed and are all

statistically insignificant within the limits at $\alpha = 5\%$. The Q-statistic modified by Box and Ljung (1978) can also be used to check for the insignificance of the autocorrelations.

2.2.33 Forecasting

One of the most important objectives of time series analysis is to forecast its future values. The general theory of linear prediction was developed by Kolmogorov (1939, 1941), Wiener (1949), Kalman (1960), and Whittle (1983).

CHAPTER THREE

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

3.1 INTRODUCTION

The presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data acquired for this study are covered in this chapter. The secondary data utilized for this study was obtained from University of Ilorin Teaching Hospital and it contains the number of malaria patient from 2013 to 2023. The time series pattern was observed, examined, and analyzed.

3.2 DATA PRESENTATION

Table 5: The number of malaria patients in University of Ilorin Hospital Ilorin, Kwara State

Month/Year	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Jan	118	44	25	34	44	13	61	18	10	18	48
Feb	90	45	32	22	40	19	150	13	26	18	51
Mar	72	32	14	15	26	26	40	38	20	9	30
Apr	148	38	33	36	19	24	63	27	17	9	44
May	120	52	42	35	56	23	42	53	19	56	25
Jun	67	54	61	12	59	44	49	41	30	72	29
Jul	76	39	123	83	52	72	90	33	35	63	31
Aug	56	36	124	58	27	116	112	35	24	96	23
Sep	52	27	95	45	19	93	87	53	19	62	25
Oct	41	12	111	36	34	87	64	25	35	34	33
Nov	78	34	66	8	22	156	84	27	19	43	22
Dec	50	28	11	13	13	61	57	25	53	35	15

Table 6: Statistics of Number of Malaria Patient in UITH (2013-2023)

Measures	Min	Max	Mean	Median	Variance	Standard Error	Q3	Q1	Skewness	Kurtosis
Output	8.00	156	46.7	37	1004.12	2.76	59.5	25	1.3814	4.6684

Interpretation: The monthly patient count ranged from 8 to 156. The average count was about 47 patients per month, but the distribution was right-skewed, indicating more months with above-average patients. The variance of 1004.12 and a standard error of 2.76 highlight the substantial variability in the monthly patient count. The lower quartile (25) and upper quartile (60) indicate that 50% of the months had between 25 and 60 patients. The skewness of 1.3814 and kurtosis of 4.6684 suggest a distribution with heavy tails and a sharp peak, indicating the presence of outliers or extreme values in the data.

3.3 TIME PLOT FOR NUMBER OF MALARAIA PATIENT AT UITH

Figure 8: Time plot of number of malaria patient in UITH

The time plot of the monthly number of malaria patients in UITH shown above shows upward and downward movement. The spikes present in the time plot indicates that there are in the number of malaria patient at UITH. The presence of steps also indicates a sudden change in the number of people affected with malaria. The time plot shows the presence of seasonality, trend and random component of time series.

3.4 ESTIMATION OF THE COMPONENT OF TIME SERIES IN NUMBER OF MALARIA PATIENTS IN UITH (2013-2023)

Table 7: The Component of Time Series in Number of Malaria Patients in UITH (2013-2023)

S/N	Time	Seasonal	Trend	Remainder
1	Jan 2013	-11.73871	119.82556	9.9131539
2	Feb 2013	-4.1101295	112.67405	-18.563919
3	Mar 2013	-19.8452043	105.52254	-13.6773365
4	Apr 2013	-6.7620812	98.76732	55.9947596
5	May 2013	-0.1334782	92.01210	28.1213758
6	Jun 2013	0.0147836	85.76266	-18.7774419
7	Jul 2013	16.8903217	79.51321	-20.4035359
8	Aug 2013	18.4413115	73.37279	-35.8140972
9	Sep 2013	7.2650182	67.23236	-22.4973754
10	Oct 2013	2.2620332	61.70187	-22.9639054
11	Nov 2013	7.4408662	56.17139	14.3877466
12	Dec 2013	-9.7247288	53.39796	6.3267693
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
128	Aug 2023	18.4413115	66.84833	26.7103589
129	Sep 2023	7.2650182	63.24634	16.4886449
130	Oct 2023	2.2620332	60.78037	0.9575951
131	Nov 2023	7.4408662	58.31441	-12.8534379
132	Dec 2023	-9.7247288	55.51636	11.2083692

Interpretation: The component is additively related. This implies that the time series has roughly the same variability through the length of the series.

3.5 DECOMPOSITION OF THE ADDITIVE TIME SERIES

Figure 9: Decomposition of the additive time series of the number of malaria patient in UITH

Interpretation: The decomposition of the time series data on monthly malaria patients at UITH from 2013 to 2023 reveals an underlying trend, seasonal fluctuations, and random variations in the observed data.

3.6 TEST OF STATIONARITY

Using Augmented Dickey Fuller test of the original series

Hypothesis

H₀: the series of the original data is not stationary

Versus

H₁: the series of the original data is stationary

Decision rule: Reject H₀ p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance, otherwise do not reject null hypothesis

Table 8:Summary of the Augmented Dickey Fuller

Test	Test Statistics	Sig	Lag order	p-value
ADF	-3.8541	0.05	5	0.01855

Conclusion: since our test p-value (0.01855) is less than the level of significance (0.05), We accept the null hypothesis and conclude that the monthly number of malaria patient data is stationary.

3,7 AUTOCORRELATION FUNCTION (ACF) AND PARTIAL AUTOCORRELATION FUNCTION (PACF)

Models are identified through patterns in their ACFs (autocorrelation functions) and PACFs (partial autocorrelation functions). Both autocorrelations and partial autocorrelations is shown below.

ACF PLOT OF ORIGINAL DATA

Figure 10: Autocorrelation Function Plot of the number of malaria patient

PACF PLOT OF ORIGINAL DATA

Figure 11: Partial Autocorrelation of the number of malaria patient

Interpretation: From figure 2 and figure 3 respectively, the ACF plot above, there is a significant spike at lag 1, 2 and 3. Then the lags die off. And this may suggest a moving average parameter (p) to be 3 which implies MA (3). And also, In the PACF, there is a significant spike at lag 2 and 3. And this suggest autoregressive parameter (q) to be 2 which implies AR (2).

3.8 ESTIMATION OF ARIMA MODEL

Several plausible ARIMA model using different combinations of q and p parameters were fitted to the data. The best model is the model with the smallest AICc criterion.

Table 5: Estimation of ARIMA Models

Model	AR (1)	AR (2)	AR (3)	MA (1)	MA (2)	MA (3)	AIC	AICc
ARIMA (1,0,1)	0.781			-0.246			1226.17	1226.48
ARIMA (1,0,2)	0.797			-0.233	-0.057		1228.08	1228.56
ARIMA (1,0,3)	0.434			0.164	0.097	0.382	1216.13	1216.8
ARIMA (2,0,1)	-0.187	0.474		0.890			1227.89	1228.36
ARIMA (2,0,2)	0.171	0.512		0.462	-0.307		1223.51	1224.18
ARIMA (2,0,3)	0.358	0.095		0.233	0.063	0.357	1217.91	1218.81
ARIMA (3,0,1)	-0.039	0.301	0.327	0.617			1217.82	1218.49
ARIMA (3,0,2)	0.060	-0.361	0.664	0.464	0.810		1215.9	1216.8
ARIMA (3,0,3)	-0.117	-0.240	0.498	0.732	0.741	0.260	1214.93	1216.1

Interpretation: The above shows the possible combinations of the ARIMA model. From the output we can deduce that the best model is ARIMA (3,0,3) because it has the least AIC (1214.93) and AICc (1216.1) value.

3.9 PARAMETER OF THE BEST MODEL

Table 6: ARIMA (3,0,3)

Coefficient	Value	Standard Error
ar1	-0.1166	0.1315
ar2	-0.2398	0.2470
ar3	0.4982	0.1268
ma1	0.7324	0.1488
ma2	0.7406	0.2985
ma3	0.2596	0.1415
Intercept	47.1130	6.1623

Interpretation: The coefficient of ARIMA (3,0,3) model are valid, since the coefficients were all less than one and stationary condition was met and satisfied. The fitted model of ARIMA(3,0,3) is expressed as

$$y_t = c + \phi_1 y_{t-1} + \phi_2 y_{t-2} + \phi_3 y_{t-3} + \theta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} + \theta_2 \varepsilon_{t-2} + \theta_3 \varepsilon_{t-3} + \varepsilon_t$$
$$y_t = 47.1130 - 0.1166y_{t-1} - 0.2398y_{t-2} + 0.4982y_{t-3} + 0.7324\varepsilon_{t-1} + 0.7406\varepsilon_{t-2} + 0.2596\varepsilon_{t-3}$$

3.10 DIAGNOSTIC CHECKING OF THE FITTED MODEL

We are going to carry out a diagnostic test to ascertain the adequacy of the fitted model. This can be done by plotting the ACF and PACF of the residuals of the fitted model and Box-Ljung Test.

PACF AND ACF PLOT OF THE RESIDUALS OF THE FITTED MODEL

Figure 12: Plot of the Residuals of the fitted model

Figure 13: Autocorrelation Function of the Residual of the Fitted Model

Figure 14: Partial Autocorrelation Function of the Residual of the Fitted Model

Interpretation: Since all the ACF and PACF of residual of the fitted model lies within the significance bounds, this shows that the model is adequate.

3.11 BOX -LJUNG TEST FOR DIAGNOSTIC CHECKING OF ARIMA MODEL

Hypothesis

H₀: There is non-zero autocorrelations in the model errors

Versus

H₁: There is zero autocorrelations in the model errors

Decision rule: Reject H₀ p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance, otherwise do not reject null hypothesis

Table 7: Summary of The Box-Ljung Test

Test	X-squared	Sig	Df	p-value
Box-Pierce	0.064742	0.05	1	0.7992

Conclusion: The p-value for the Ljung-Box test is 0.7992 (i.e p-value is greater than 0.05), we can conclude that there is evidence for non-zero autocorrelation in the forecast errors. Which implies that the model is adequate.

3.12 FORECASTING

This section creates a projection into the future from its historical values based on the ARIMA model that accurately covers the evolution of the series

The fitted ARIMA (3,0,3) is used to predict the monthly number of the malaria cases in UITH Ilorin for two years.

Table 8: The fitted ARIMA (3,0,3) is used to predict the monthly number of reported cases of malaria patients in UITH Ilorin for two years.

Month	Point Forecast	80% Lower Bound	80% Upper Bound	95% Lower Bound	95% Upper Bound
Jan 2024	29.17	0.23	58.12	-15.09	73.44
Feb 2024	29.49	-4.51	63.48	-22.50	81.47
Mar 2024	33.31	-2.88	69.49	-22.04	88.65
Apr 2024	44.01	4.36	83.67	-16.63	104.66
May 2024	42.00	2.15	81.86	-18.95	102.96
Jun 2024	41.57	1.68	81.47	-19.44	102.59
Jul 2024	47.44	6.95	87.93	-14.48	109.36
Aug 2024	45.86	5.36	86.35	-16.08	107.79
Sep 2024	44.42	3.92	84.93	-17.53	106.37
Oct 2024	47.89	7.25	88.54	-14.27	110.05
Nov 2024	47.04	6.40	87.69	-15.12	109.20
Dec 2024	45.59	4.93	86.26	-16.60	107.78
Jan 2025	47.69	6.99	88.40	-14.55	109.94

Feb 2025	47.37	6.67	88.08	-14.88	109.62
Mar 2025	46.19	5.47	86.90	-16.08	108.46
Apr 2025	47.45	6.72	88.18	-14.84	109.74
May 2025	47.43	6.70	88.15	-14.86	109.72
Jun 2025	46.53	5.80	87.27	-15.77	108.83
Jul 2025	47.27	6.53	88.01	-15.03	109.58
Aug 2025	47.39	6.65	88.13	-14.92	109.70
Sep 2025	46.75	6.01	87.50	-15.56	109.07
Oct 2025	47.17	6.42	87.91	-15.15	109.48
Nov 2025	47.33	6.58	88.08	-14.98	109.64
Dec 2025	46.90	6.15	87.64	-15.42	109.21

Table 8, shows the forecast for the number of malaria patient in UITH for the year 2024 and 2025 using ARIMA (3,0,3). The point forecast indicates the model's exact prediction for the year 2024 and 2025. It also shows the 80% and 95% confident interval.

Table 9: The extracted forecast point for the year 2024 and 2025

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
2024	29	29	33	44	42	42	47	46	44	48	47	46
2025	48	47	46	47	47	47	47	47	47	47	47	47

Table 10, shows that the average number of malaria cases over the two years is approximately 44 per month. The number of malaria cases will range from at least 29 in the early months of 2024 to at most 48 in late 2024 and early 2025, indicating initial fluctuations followed by consistent numbers throughout 2025.

Forecast from ARIMA (3,0,3)

Figure 8: Forecast from the ARIMA (3,0,3) model applied to the monthly number of malaria patient in UITH

CHAPTER FOUR

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

4.1 SUMMARY

The analysis of malaria patient data from the University of Ilorin Teaching Hospital (UIITH) from 2013 to 2023 began with a time plot, which illustrated significant fluctuations in cases of malaria patient throughout the years. The time plot revealed both upward and downward trends, with noticeable spikes and steps indicating periods of unusual patient counts. This visual representation highlighted the presence of seasonality, trends, and random variations in the data.

Decomposition of the time series data showed that the observed patient numbers could be decompose into seasonal effects, underlying trends, and random variations. The original data was confirmed as stationary through the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test, with a p-value of 0.01855, which implies differencing was not applied. Autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation plots suggested that an ARIMA model would be suitable with an order of differencing to be zero.

The best-fit ARIMA model identified was ARIMA (3,0,3), which included three autoregressive terms and three moving average terms. The fitted model of ARIMA(3,0,3) was expressed as $y_t = 47.1130 - 0.1166y_{t-1} - 0.2398y_{t-2} + 0.4982y_{t-3} + 0.7324\varepsilon_{t-1} + 0.7406\varepsilon_{t-2} + 0.2596\varepsilon_{t-3}$

This model had the lowest AIC values, suggesting it provides the most accurate representation of the data. Diagnostic checks, including residual plots and the Box-Ljung test, confirmed that the model was adequate and did not exhibit significant autocorrelation in the residuals.

Using the ARIMA (3,0,3) model, forecasts were made for the number of malaria patients for 2024 and 2025. The predictions indicated that the monthly incidence of malaria cases would range from 29 to 49 in 2024 and from 40 to 49 in 2025 if the trends in the observed data continued without any interventions from any quarters

4.2 CONCLUSION

The analysis of malaria data from UITH (2013-2023) highlighted significant trends and fluctuations. The ARIMA (3,0,3) model's forecasts suggest monthly patient numbers will range from 29 to 49 in 2024 and 40 to 49 in 2025.

To address these trends, UITH should adjust resources and staffing accordingly. Additionally, to reduce malaria spread, enhance mosquito control measures, promote the use of mosquito nets and ensure prompt diagnosis and treatment of malaria cases. Regular updates to forecasting models will support effective healthcare planning.

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